

Sequential Block Elimination for Dynamic Pricing

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Abstract—In this paper, we propose a Thompson Sampling based sequential block elimination approach for dynamic pricing within pure-exploration Multi-Armed Bandit (MAB) setting. Given an l -dimensional action space, which represents various price ranges, our objective is to identify the optimal prices for different alternatives or variants of a product in order to maximize the total revenue. Our contribution lies in the development of a novel block elimination-based MAB algorithm. The proposed algorithm begins by discretizing the continuous action space into a finite set of discrete actions. Subsequently, a recursive block elimination procedure is employed to progressively remove sub-optimal actions from the set. The elimination process leverages the calculation of confidence bounds over the blocks of actions, enabling the efficient exclusion of sub-optimal choices. We conduct extensive experiments on a dynamic pricing problem in the logistics domain to evaluate the effectiveness of our proposed approach. The experimental results demonstrate that our method is able to identify the optimal arms within the given budget.

Index Terms—Sequential Learning, Multi-Armed Bandits, Thompson Sampling, Learning with Feedback, Pure-Exploration, Dynamic Pricing

I. INTRODUCTION

It is a widespread practice among online business providers to market different variants of the same product to cater to diverse customer preferences and requirements. For instance, in the logistics sector, multiple levels of delivery services are typically offered for the same source-destination pair. Companies like DHL provide both express and economy services, while UPS similarly offers standard and express delivery options. Mobility service providers such as Bolt and Lyft also offer customers the flexibility to choose from different ride service variants, such as standard rides or shared rides. In the e-commerce industry, it is common to see various configurations of the same product available for purchase, such as a pack of five chocolate bars versus a pack of ten. These product variants are designed to meet the varying needs of customers and enable businesses to optimize revenue by offering differentiated pricing options for similar products.

A recurring problem in the aforementioned problem setting is the challenge of identifying the optimal prices to be assigned to different variants of the services or products to maximize expected revenues. The primary challenge here is that the

demand curves for different services and product variants are not known to the decision-maker beforehand. However, the decision-maker has the flexibility to dynamically adjust the assigned prices and, in many cases, to randomize these price adjustments in order to ‘learn’ the optimal pricing strategy over time. This continuous experimentation allows for the exploration of customer responses to various pricing configurations, gradually revealing the demand curve and enabling the identification of the price points that maximize revenue.

In practice, offline price experiments are often conducted using the principle of “learn, then earn” where decision-makers first gather sufficient information on customer preferences before setting the optimal prices. In contrast, Multi-Armed Bandit (MAB) algorithms adopt a more dynamic approach known as “learn-while-earn” [1], enabling simultaneous learning and revenue optimization. This approach offers greater flexibility in experimentation, allowing the decision-maker to continually adjust prices based on real-time feedback. As a result, MAB algorithms can significantly improve the efficiency of the experiment design and reduce overall costs by minimizing revenue loss during the learning phase. Several MAB-based adaptive learning algorithms have been proposed for dynamic pricing in recent years [1, 2, 3, 4]. These approaches leverage the inherent trade-off between exploration and exploitation, enabling businesses to refine their pricing strategies more effectively under uncertainty.

Historically, pure-exploration multi-armed bandit algorithms have been employed for optimal arm identification [5, 6, 7, 8], aiming to choose the most rewarding action from a set of available actions. However, the direct application of these algorithms to dynamic pricing problems presents unique challenges, as they often require evaluating all possible action combinations at least once to ensure accurate identification. This condition becomes impractical in real-world dynamic pricing situations because the number of possible actions (price combinations) might be exceedingly large. Moreover, current pure-exploration algorithms typically presuppose a fixed and rather small action space, rendering them inappropriate for continuous action spaces often encountered in pricing problems. Although certain infinite or continuous-armed bandit algorithms mitigate these limitations by utilising structural

characteristics of the action space, such as Lipschitz continuity [9, 10], and discretising the action space to formulate more efficient algorithms, these approaches still possess a significant drawback: they necessitate sampling each discretised action at least once. Many of these approaches are based on the widely used Upper Confidence Bound (UCB) algorithm [11], which, despite being effective in certain settings, faces inherent limitations when applied to dynamic pricing. Estimating revenues by enumerating all possible combinations, even within a discretized framework, can be computationally intensive and economically unfeasible.

One workaround is to use coarse-grained discretization to reduce the number of actions, making the problem more computationally manageable. However, this can lead to the omission of the optimal action, as it may overlook critical differences between potentially high-performing actions. An alternative strategy is to employ *action elimination*, where sub-optimal actions are progressively discarded during exploration based on their estimated confidence values. This technique focuses exploration on more promising actions, reducing the number of evaluations needed while still enabling the identification of the optimal action [8, 12, 13]. To our knowledge, all elimination-based Multi-Armed Bandit (MAB) algorithms in the literature either require sampling each action at least once [12, 13] or selecting a representative action, such as the most central one [8]. While these methods ensure coverage of the action space or reduce sampling needs, they are limited by the necessity to evaluate a predefined set of actions, which can be impractical in high-dimensional, continuous-action environments.

In this paper, we present an innovative *block elimination*-based Multi-Armed Bandit (MAB) algorithm. Our approach significantly differs from existing elimination-based pure-exploration algorithms by enabling the decision-maker to recursively eliminate *blocks of actions* through confidence scoring. This technique facilitates a systematic and efficient reduction of the action space, aiding in the identification of optimal actions without requiring individual evaluations. Our algorithms employ Thompson Sampling, a straightforward yet powerful heuristic for MAB problems that offers a demonstrable optimality guarantee [14, 15, 16]. While Thompson Sampling has traditionally shown efficacy in pure-exploration scenarios [17, 18], our method diverges from previous elimination-based approaches by not requiring the sampling of each individual action before making elimination decisions. Instead, it leverages confidence bounds for early eliminations, thereby reducing the need for extensive sampling. This feature enhances the practicality and applicability of our approach, particularly in dynamic assignment problems where decision-makers face time or budget constraints.

II. RELATED WORK

Over the last decade, various methods for pure-exploration bandits have emerged, primarily derived from the well-known Upper Confidence Bound (UCB) algorithm [11]. The pure-exploration bandit problem is analyzed from two perspectives:

(i) fixed-confidence scenarios, where the goal is to minimize the rounds required to identify an action meeting a specified confidence level relative to the optimal action, and (ii) fixed-budget scenarios, which aim to identify the optimal action within a given number of rounds. Fixed-confidence algorithms optimize budget for a specific confidence level, while fixed-budget algorithms focus on minimizing trials needed to achieve a predetermined confidence level. It is widely acknowledged that the fixed-budget setting is significantly more challenging [19].

Given that our research operates within a limited budget framework, we will focus exclusively on literature related to fixed-budget pure-exploration bandit algorithms. For readers seeking further information, we recommend [5, 7, 13, 19, 20] for a comprehensive review of fixed-confidence pure-exploration algorithms.

Elimination-based algorithms have proven more effective in fixed-budget scenarios, as they systematically discard poor actions until only a unique or near-optimal action remains [19]. In their seminal work, [5] introduced the successive reject method, which partitions the trial budget into $k - 1$ elimination phases, systematically eliminating the arm with the lowest empirical mean at the end of each phase. A primary limitation is the requirement for each action to be sampled at least once, making it unsuitable when the action set is significantly larger than the available budget. Furthermore, this method necessitates prior knowledge of a problem-specific parameter.

The Sequential Halving (SH) algorithm [12] resembles the successive reject method. In SH, the budget is uniformly distributed across $\log_2 T$ represents the budget. In each phase, actions are sampled equally to update empirical mean values, and the lowest-performing 50% are discarded at the end. Similar to the successive reject method, SH requires that each action be sampled at least once, limiting its applicability when the action set exceeds the budget.

In [8], the authors introduce the Sequential Block Elimination (SBE) algorithm, which uniformly distributes the budget throughout the elimination phase and eliminates blocks of actions rather than individual actions. The algorithm uses auxiliary information to construct action blocks, sampling the central action in each iteration. At the end of each elimination phase, the block with the lowest empirical mean reward for the central action is eliminated. Recently, [21] proposed the Variance-Based Rejects (VBR) algorithm, which operates in stages, sampling all non-eliminated actions for a predetermined number of rounds to estimate their empirical mean rewards and standard deviations. Unlike other algorithms, VBR uses a confidence score derived from empirical means for its exclusion criteria. Actions with an upper bound lower than the current maximal lower bound are discarded after each elimination phase. However, this approach also struggles to scale when the action set significantly exceeds the budget.

III. SEQUENTIAL BLOCK ELIMINATION FRAMEWORK

In a stochastic Multi-Armed Bandit (MAB) problem, k actions, a budget of T rounds, and k unknown reward distributions ν_1, \dots, ν_k are considered. At each round t , the decision-maker selects an action I_t and receives a reward drawn from its corresponding distribution. In the pure-exploration setting, the decision-maker recommends an action J_t after each round, aiming to minimize expected loss (or maximize reward) with high confidence. Rewards are observed only for I_t , but evaluation depends solely on J_t , distinguishing it from the classical MAB framework.

We consider smooth reward functions, specifically Lipschitz continuous functions, following prior work [9, 10, 22]. Our problem is framed as a Lipschitz bandit problem within an l -dimensional metric space, where the metric is determined by the Lipschitz condition [22]. Here, \mathcal{X} represents the l -dimensional action space with an unknown reward function satisfying the Lipschitz condition. At each round, the decision-maker selects an action $x \in \mathcal{X}$ and receives a reward based on the reward distribution of x . The goal is to identify the action with the highest expected reward. In our application, l corresponds to the number of variants of the products or services.

Thompson Sampling is a Bayesian heuristic for solving multi-armed bandit problems. At each step, the decision-maker samples parameters of the reward distribution from a prior distribution and selects the action based on its posterior probability of being optimal. For Bernoulli-distributed rewards, Thompson Sampling outperforms UCB-based algorithms, even with prior mismatches (using the Beta distribution as the conjugate prior). In our setting, where rewards are positive real numbers, we model them using a log-normal distribution. We specify Gamma and Normal priors for the precision (inverse variance) and mean of the underlying normal distribution that defines the log-normal distribution, respectively.

The precision ($\tau_{i_{t+1}} = \frac{1}{\sigma^2}$) and mean ($\mu_{i_{t+1}}$) for the action i at round $t + 1$ are sampled as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_{i_{t+1}} | r_{I_t} &\sim \Gamma \left(\alpha + \frac{n_{i_t}}{2}, \beta + \frac{1}{2} \text{SSE} + \frac{n_{i_t} (\bar{y}_i - y_0)^2}{2(n_{i_t} + 1)} \right) \\ \mu_{i_{t+1}} | r_{i_t}, \tau_{i_{t+1}} &\sim \mathcal{N} \left(\frac{n_{i_t} \bar{y}_i + 1}{n_{i_t} + 1}, (n_{i_t} + 1) \tau_{i_{t+1}} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

In the expressions provided above, the constants α , β , and y_0 are fixed values. The variable n_{i_t} represents the number of times the action i is selected up to round t . Additionally, $y_i = \ln(r_i)$, where r_i denotes the reward associated with action i . The term \bar{y}_i corresponds to the empirical mean of y_i calculated over the rounds up to time t . The sum of squared errors, denoted as SSE, is defined as the summation of the squared differences between y_i and the empirical mean \bar{y}_i . Mathematically, this is expressed as follows: $\text{SSE} = \sum (y_i - \bar{y}_i)^2$

Given the prior mean (μ_t) and precision (τ_t) vectors, the rewards are sampled according to:

$$\mathbf{r}_t | \mu_{t-1}, \tau_{t-1} \sim \text{LogNormal} \left(\mu_{t-1}, \sqrt{\frac{1}{\tau_{t-1}}} \right) \quad (2)$$

A. Block Elimination Mechanism

Our algorithm starts by discretizing the continuous action space, a standard practice in Lipschitz bandits for applying MAB algorithms like UCB [9, 10]. As our method does not require sampling all actions, we use fine-grained discretization. We discretize all price values independently to form clusters, or blocks, of actions. Similar to other elimination-based algorithms [8, 12, 21], our approach operates in phases.

The pseudo-code in Algorithm 1 details our block-elimination method. The mean and the precision of rewards of all the discretized actions are initialized to one and two respectively. In line:7, the decision-maker chooses the action with the highest reward according to the current prior estimation of the mean and precision of the rewards. Then, it observes the actual reward from the chosen action and updates its mean reward in line:9. After the κ -th round, the decision-maker invokes procedure `Eliminate` to eliminate actions or blocks of actions based on the calculated confidence scores.

The pseudo-code for `Eliminate` is provided in Algorithm:7. It takes the discretized action set \mathcal{A} , the observed mean reward vector μ and the current round t as the input. It first checks whether the non-eliminated action set is large enough to be clustered or not. In each invocation of the `Eliminate`, the algorithm reduces the block size to zoom into the promising non-eliminated actions. To cluster actions, one can employ tree-based space-partitioning as in [23] or simple distance-based clustering algorithms like KMeans [24]. In line:1 of `Eliminate`, the decision-maker calculates the lower and upper confidence bounds on the mean reward for each cluster. A visual demonstration and worked-out example of the proposed blocking algorithm are given at the end of this section.

Our elimination is based on the observation that the algorithm will not benefit by exploring actions whose potential mean rewards are lower compared to alternative actions with high rewards. Based on this observation, we devise an elimination rule: *we eliminate the blocks whose upper confidence bound on the mean reward value is lower than the maximum of the lower confidence bounds on the mean reward.*

B. Confidence Bound Estimation

In Algorithm:7, we find the maximum lower bound at line:2 and then check the upper bound of each cluster, thus, removing the least rewarding actions. The main challenge we face here is that since an eliminated block or arm is never revisited, each elimination should be made with high confidence. Hence, we adopt two confidence estimation schemes:

a) *Standard Error-based Bound Estimation*:: In [21], the authors proposed a standard error-based elimination where $\text{lbs} = \mu - \gamma \cdot \sigma$ and $\text{ubs} = \mu + \gamma \cdot \sigma$. We calculate the

Algorithm 1: Recursive Block Elimination

Input : \mathcal{X}, T, κ

- 1 $\mathcal{A} = \text{Discretize}(\mathcal{X})$;
- 2 $p = |\mathcal{A}|$, $\alpha = 1$, $\beta = 1$, $y_0 = 1$;
- 3 $\mathcal{C} = \text{cluster}(\mathcal{A})$;
- 4 $\mu_{i,0} = 1 \forall i = 1 \dots p$; // initial mean reward vector
- 5 $\tau_{i,0} = 2 \forall i = 1 \dots p$; // initial precision vector
- 6 **for** $t = 1, 2, \dots, T$ **do**
- 7 $I_t = \text{argmax}_i \text{LogNormal}\left(\mu_{i,t-1}, \sqrt{\frac{1}{\tau_{i,t-1}}}\right)$;
- 8 play arm I_t and observe reward r_{I_t} ;
- 9 update $\mu_{I_t,t}$ & $\tau_{I_t,t}$;
- 10 update mean and precision of cluster;
- 11 **if** $(t \% \kappa == 0)$ **then**
- 12 | Eliminate(\mathcal{C}, μ_t, t)
- 13 **return** action with highest mean;

Algorithm 2: Eliminate Procedure

- 1 $(lbs, ub) = \text{GetConfidenceBounds}(\mathcal{C}, \mu)$;
// estimate lower and upper bounds
- 2 $maxlb = \max(lbs)$;
- 3 **for** $i \in \mathcal{C}$ **do**
- 4 **if** $(ubs[i] \leq maxlb)$ **then**
- 5 | eliminate action(s) from \mathcal{A} corresponding to
| block i
- 6 $\mathcal{C} = \text{cluster}(\mathcal{A})$; // recursively cluster
non-eliminated actions
- 7 **return** \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C}

mean and variance of a cluster by considering the rewards of all actions in that cluster. The γ is a constant that measures the confidence. We set $\gamma = 2$ in our implementation, achieving $\sim 90\%$ confidence interval.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

In this section, we provide preliminary results of our experiments. We evaluate the performance of our approach in dynamic pricing settings using synthetic dataset carefully modeled using real-world data. Our objective is to determine optimal prices for two variants of a logistic service, aiming to maximize total revenue. To illustrate, we considered two logistic services ($l = 2$): (i) Standard and (ii) Express. The minimum and maximum prices for the ‘standard’ service were set to 10 and 50, respectively, while for the ‘express’ service, they were set to 30 and 70 (in a monetary unit).

a) Revenue Data Generation: The revenue function for the experiment is modelled based on a recent study using real data [25] and is defined as: $r = p_1 c_1 + p_2 c_2$, where p_1 represents the probability of choosing the standard option, and p_2 is the probability of opting for the express service.

Fig. 1. Contour map after running algorithm for 100 rounds

Additionally, c_1 and c_2 denote the numbers of customers who chose options standard and express, respectively, based on the probabilities p_1 and p_2 . The probabilities are further defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 z_2 &= \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-\alpha_2 a_2 - \beta_2)} \\
 z_1 &= (1 - z_2) \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-\alpha_1 a_1 - \beta_1)} \\
 p_1 &= \frac{z_1}{z_1 + z_2} \text{ and } p_2 = \frac{z_2}{z_1 + z_2}
 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

Here $\alpha_1 = -0.05$, $\alpha_2 = -0.05$, $\beta_1 = -0.5$ and $\beta_2 = 2$ are constants and a_1 and a_2 are prices for standard and express respectively.

A. Results

Our preliminary results are plotted in Figure 1 which shows the contours of price ranges with the eliminated and recommended prices after the end of 100 rounds. These visuals illustrate how effectively our algorithms eliminate sub-optimal blocks of actions, regardless of the size and shape of the optimal region, in comparison to baseline strategies. Specifically, the plots showcase the *ground truth* optimal pair of solutions and the achieved solution by our algorithm. Actions marked in cyan color are eliminated, and those marked with ‘+’ are played actions. Notably, our algorithm successfully eliminate most suboptimal actions within the 100-round budget and recommend the action closest to the optimal solution.

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